

The Effectiveness of a Prediabetes Protocol for Diabetes Prevention

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Background

- Prediabetes is a significant risk factor in the development of T2DM that affects a vast majority of the population
 - Nearly 100 million Americans live with prediabetes, yet most people are unaware they have the condition (CDC, 2021)
 - Lifestyle changes can decrease glucose levels and significantly reduce weight in individuals, decreasing the incidence of other comorbidities (ADA, 2021; CDC, 2021a; O'Brien et al., 2017)
 - Diabetic prevention programs (DPP) provide a structured lifestyle change program
- According to the CDC (2021), DPPs can decrease the risk of developing diabetes by nearly 60% in adults and over 70% in those 60 and older

Purpose

To outline the severe health risks attached to the diagnosis of T2DM and highlight the benefits that DPPs and lifestyle interventions have on an individual's health and in the prevention of T2DM

To develop, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based prediabetes protocol, including a pilot DPP targeting prediabetic patients in a Los Angeles, California, primary care clinic

Methods

- **Design:** Pre- and post-test pilot DPP with the following measures: a questionnaire, weight (lbs), BMI, blood pressure, and hemoglobin A1c (HgbA1c)
- **Setting:** A primary care clinic in Los Angeles, CA
- **Participants:** Prediabetic adults ages 30-60
- **Intervention:** Attending ten classes on diabetes prevention over ten weeks
- **Statistical analysis:** Descriptive statistics

Results

Framework: Health Belief Model

(Champion & Skinner, 2008, p. 49)

Recommendations

- Implementation of a prediabetes protocol for all prediabetic patients
- Offering virtual and in-person classes as an option
- Offering classes at different times of the week
- Offering the option of weekly or monthly classes
- Have clinicians teach classes

Limitations

- Small sample size
- A short study period of ten weeks
- Self-reported surveys
- Participants selected were from the same clinic, reducing generalizability
- Some participants did not join due to unfamiliarity with the utilization of online classes and technical difficulties
- Primarily female participants

Implications

- DPPs can provide positive health outcomes
- There should be a focus on implementing DPPs in the clinical setting to prevent T2DM and provide other health benefits

References

